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Employee Performance and Human Capital Politics in Public Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria (A Study of University of Ilorin, Ilorin and Benue State University Markudi)

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ABSTRACT

The decline in academic performance has been a topic that various thinkers have questioned. However, the politics of human capital on employee performance in Nigerian public universities remains underexplored. This study investigates the relationship between the

politics of human capital and employee performance in Nigerian public universities, focusing on the University of Ilorin (Unilorin) and Benue State University (BSU). The study aims to evaluate the degree of nepotism in the selection of staff for human capital development, assess the politics of standard operating procedures in the selection of staff for human capital development, and examine job performance. A mixed-methods design was employed, with a sample size of 378 academic and administrative staff from 6717. The findings reveal a significant relationship between HCP and employee performance. The HCP01 (training and skill development) has the strongest relationship, while HCP02 and HCP03 (educational qualifications and background, and innovation or leadership development) have weaker relationships. The study recommends, among others, the need for merit-based exercises and anti-nepotism policies, empowered by law, to ensure equitable access to development opportunities, in collaboration with regulatory bodies, to strengthen Human capital advancement.

Keywords: *Cronyism, Institution, Employee, Politics, Staff, Promotion.*

INTRODUCTION

Politics is a global practice in both formal and informal sectors that shapes the dynamics of activities in any organization. Politics in the university involve difference stakeholders both within and outside the University. Politics often determines the authoritative allocation of value in terms of appointments, funding allocations, and policy implementation within the University Community, which reflects on the standard. Universities are very important institutions in the development of any nation because they help build human capital, foster innovation, and produce knowledge, which are paramount for economic development and the overall growth of a society. The success the universities achieve in executing these roles, however, is greatly dependent on the nature and development of human capital. Job performance among academic and non-academic staff in Nigerian universities is a controversial phenomenon, despite numerous policies and reforms aimed at improving human capital in the country's universities (Ofor-Douglas, 2023). This disjuncture begs the question of

the political, structural, and institutional processes defining Human Capital Development (HCD) and their interaction with job performance.

Favouritism is a unique tendency practiced in all countries of the world, whether in America, Europe, or Asia. Favouritism comes in different shades like cronyism, patronage, nepotism, and even racism. University favouritism gives special privileges, unequal treatment, and access to university resources, and grants unequal benefits to members of one group based on primordial sentiment. In fact, it is now becoming a new normal in Ghana's higher institutions that securing employment opportunities in universities is determined by who you know, no matter one's qualifications, appropriate experience, or skills (Joseph and Alhassan 2023).

In the United Kingdom, universities gain from strong regulatory oversight, strategic alignment with national goals, and huge investment in research infrastructure. Institutions such as Oxford and Cambridge exemplify the integration of teaching, research, and innovation, supported by mechanisms like the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and the Quality Assurance Agency (QAA). Similarly, the United States higher education system is marked by decentralisation, robust public-private partnerships, and faculty empowerment through tenure and competitive grants. Universities like Harvard and MIT maintain strong industry linkages and lead in digital education, enhancing both access and personalization. These systems are designed to align academic outputs with labour market needs, foster global talent, and sustain long-term institutional excellence (O'Neil & Bagchi-Sen, 2023).

In contrast, African universities operate within complex socio-economic cum political contexts that present both opportunities and challenges for human capital development. Institutions such as the University of Ibadan and University of Nairobi face continue challenges in so many areas which include underfunding, brain drain, and curriculum misalignment with labour market demands. Despite these constraints,

regional initiatives like the African Economic Research Consortium (AERC, 2023) and the Association of African Universities (AAU) are promoting capacity building and policy reform. African universities are increasingly engaging in strategic partnerships and regional collaboration to address systemic gaps. While the UK and US have established models that support innovation and competitiveness, African institutions are navigating structural challenges with growing momentum for reform. Specifically, the challenges faced by Nigeria first generation institutions such as ABU, UNN, UI and others reflect broader systemic issues within Nigeria's higher education sector. Addressing these problems requires a multi-faceted approach which includes political, economic, and strategic partnerships with industry. Without deliberate and sustained efforts to strengthen human capital development, these institutions risk falling short of their mandate to drive national progress through education and research (Center for African Studies, 2023).

Institutions such as Ahmadu Bello University (ABU) Zaria, University of Nigeria Nsukka (UNN), University of Ibadan (UI) and others continue to grapple with systemic challenges that hinder their capacity to develop and retain high-quality human capital as a result of politics that influences capacity development (Bello, 2021). Politics often shapes who gets what in the University community over the years. For instance, the appointment of Prof Saburi Oladeni Biobaku as against Prof Eni Njoku by the government of Tafawa Balewa administration after initial three years signalled political and ethnic manipulation in favour of Prof Biobaku. Politics is a global practice that comes under different shades; racism, nepotism, cronism, favouritism, and even patronage. This trend is one of the criteria for the appointments to key positions within the University, which has skewed in favor of staff loyalty to the management. Therefore, the study seeks to investigate employee performance and human capital politics at the University of Ilorin and Benue State University (now Father Adasu University, Markudi).

Statement of the Problem

The kind of politics played out in human capital development appears to affect job performance and is a critical factor in the overall success and growth of any organization, including Nigerian universities (Udu & Chukwuma, 2016). It was established that, among the challenges faced by the school administration in Turkey, favoritism is considered high, which is a major ingredient of politics in human capital development (Ismail, 2009). The University administrators' inability to meet staff needs contributed to increased staff turnover. The challenges seem to be occasioned by politics entails in lack of good working environment, poor motivation tools such as training to enhance productivity (Akinfolani and Ehinola,2014) Another major issues noticeable is the alarming rate of primordial consideration not only in the appointment, promotion but also in the training of the University staff, instead of merit base appointment and promotions affinity and connections often play leading role. Thus, it is imperative to investigate the relationship between the politics of human capital and job performance in Nigerian universities.

Research Questions

- i. How has the nepotism in the selection of staff for Human Capital Development affect job performance in University of Ilorin and Benue State University?
- ii. What has been the level of compliant with standard operating procedures in selection of staff for Human Capital Development on job performance in University of Ilorin and Benue State University?

Research objective

- To evaluate how nepotism in the selection of staff for Human Capital Development affect job performance in University of Ilorin and Benue State University.
- To assess the level of compliance of standard operating procedures in the selection of staff for Human Capital

Development on job performance in University of Ilorin and Benue State University.

Conceptual Review

Human Capital Development

Human Capital Development is defined as the set of skills and abilities an employee possesses and uses within the organization to achieve the system's goals and objectives (Eseyin, 2014). In alignment with this postulation, Aluko and Aluko (2011) stated that it is a way to fulfil people's potential by expanding their capabilities, and this necessarily implies empowering people and enabling them to participate in activities that support their own development. Ireland and Hitt (2013) aver that HCD is the summation of a person's knowledge and skills that organizations can utilize to attain their objectives. This was therefore affirmed by Morrill (2010), who emphasised that it requires integrative and systematic thinking, quantitative reasoning, collaborative decision-making, effective communication, sensitivity to narrative and values, and the capacity to work in an organised group Process. Armstrong (2004) asserts that HCD is the ability, whether inborn or acquired from institutions, that can be used by the appropriate authority for societal advancement. This aligned with the view of Achugbue and Ochonogor (2013), and Adeyemi and Ogunsola (2016) who posited that investments in human capital is a right and pragmatic step towards achieving maximum output for any organization. Ekundayo and Ajayi (2017) posit that human capital is the collection of various knowledge, talents, skills, experience, ability and wisdom available in an individual among a group of people.

The United States Economic Commission for Africa (1991) emphasizes the importance of HC, defining it as the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and physical and managerial efforts needed to utilize capital, technology, and land to create goods and services for human consumption. At a macro level, HCD involves three key capacities: developing talents, deploying those talents, and engaging in services to enhance the ability to attract talent from other sources (Mahroun, 2007). The summation and totality of the three formed the backbone of the

country competitiveness to other countries of the world (Onwumelu and Dialoke, 2018).

According to Sharma (2012) cited by Ekemam & Okpara (2020), human capital involves enhancing employees' capabilities and competencies while creating a supportive organizational environment that fosters growth. The primary goal is to boost employees' skills and performance effectiveness, ultimately driving organizational success. The growth and innovation of human capital are crucial for boosting industrial sector performance. It is evident that the degree of human capital development in any institution determines the level of buoyancy in terms of service provision or production. The failure to recognize the lucrative importance of HCD will put organizational operations in futile.

Politics

The understanding of layman place politics to mean activities that deals with political parties and politician within political party inclination. It is described as disagreement prominence in the management of political parties in the struggle for political powers in conformity with his ideology. Thus, modern political axioms have given different explanation to suit their purposes as the society evolving in the contest of understanding the term. It is conceived by Dorsey Dictionary of American government and politics as the pursuit of the political power to make binding decisions for the community and to distribute patronage and other government benefits. This view points to the fact that politics is basically concerned with the search for power and authoritative allocation of resources. This position aligned with view of David Easton that conceptualize politics as the pattern of interaction anchored toward authoritative allocation of value (Hanumanthapa, 2023). It is understood from this position that politics connotes shaping and sharing of value among people, these values were representative as safety income and difference. Appadorai (1961), considered politics as the science that dealt with the state and condition essential to its existence and development at best as described by Janet who described

politics as part of social science that treats on the foundation of state and principle of Government.

The perception of Easton captured in his presentation in 1953 on Political Science system theory or a framework in which diverse human behavior either provide input or are impacted by output within a system of a political act. The five steps approach grouped political system all are based on human behavior and actions, this aimed to turn politics into science by explaining extremely abstract model that explained the regulation of pattern and process in political life in general. Although politics is not exact science like pure and applied science but politics is considered a science in man society problem matter that should be viewed from totality rather than as a collection of problem to be solved. The primary paradigm was based on an organic vision politics, as if it were a long thing, his idea explained causes of political system to evolve and endure over the time and view politics as being in perpetual motion, rejecting the concept of equilibrium that is common in certain political system.

The political system is therefore described as a complicated cyclonical activity in which a group of process routinely convert input into output. In a political system authority established public policies. Politics as the political activities carried on in human environment to better one society economy, history and geographical environment. Hanumanthapa (2023) asserts that decision making and policies making are inextricably linked. It is however noted that not every choice constitutes a policy. Decision making is described as identification of a problem, carefully analysing potential solution and selecting one best option to give a feeling of direction for administrative convenience.

Roskin, Cord, Medeiros & Jones(2012) asserts that Aristotle was the first empirical political scientist who regarded politics as the “master science” He further defined politics as the best political community formed by citizens of the middle class, and those states are likely to be well administered in which the middle class is large ... in which the

citizens have moderate and sufficient property; for where some possess much and others nothing there may arise an extreme democracy or a pure oligarchy, or a tyranny may develop out of either extreme. ...democracies are safer and more permanent than oligarchies, because they have a middle class which is more numerous and has a greater share in government, for when there is no middle class, and the poor greatly exceed in number, troubles arise, and the state soon comes to an end". It is the believed of Aristotle about politics that the ideal political community is formed by citizens of the middle class, where individuals have moderate and sufficient property. This balance prevents the rise of extreme forms of government, such as democracy or oligarchy, which can lead to tyranny. A large middle class ensures that citizens are invested in the well-being of the state, promoting social harmony and stability. In contrast, when there is a significant wealth gap, social unrest and instability can arise, ultimately leading to the downfall of the state. Aristotle argued that democracies with a strong middle class are safer and more permanent than oligarchies, as they provide a broader base for governance and reduce the influence of extreme ideologies.

According to Wolin (2004), politics can be defined as both "a source of conflict and a mode of activity that seeks to resolve conflicts and promote readjustment". This definition emphasizes how politics can be both a cause of conflict and a tool for resolving disputes and fostering progress". This viewpoint recognizes that politics is a complicated and multidimensional arena that can lead to disputes due to divergent interests and viewpoints, but it can also be utilized to find solutions and encourage readjustment. The notion that politics is a dynamic, continuous process involving compromise, negotiation, and decision-making is supported by this concept. In line with this, Roskin (2012) claimed that the refugee German scholar of international relations Hans J. Morgenthau emphasized that "all politics is a struggle for power." Morgenthau believed that the desire for power is an inherent aspect of human nature, driving individuals and nations to constantly seek influence and assert their interests. He saw politics as a tragic and inescapable struggle for power, often leading to conflict and instability.

Job Performance

Harrison (2018) defined job performance as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioural episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period of time. This definition highlights the idea that job performance is not just about completing tasks, but also about the value those tasks bring to the organization. It emphasizes the importance of considering the specific behaviours and actions of an individual, and how they contribute to the organization's overall goals and objectives. By focusing on the expected value of an individual's behaviours, this definition provides a framework for evaluating and understanding job performance in a more nuanced and comprehensive way.

Job Performance is the bed rock of success and failure of members of staff in any organization thus achieving organization objectives (Samuel and Oyibo 2019). The continued existence of any organization can only be determined by its success which depends on its performance of its cardinal objectives over the years. The concept of job performance has received several attentions over the years, It is therefore significant to examine the concept of job performance, it is important to ascertain and consider the context within which the concept is being examined. Sabine, Judith and Anne (2019) aver that job performance could be view from employee performance, work performance, financial performance, organizational performance productivity performance, and student performance among others areas. Ali (2020) opines that the Improvement of people in an organization is the key objective of every organization. Therefore, it is of utmost importance for every organization to have outline parameters that individual's performance can be measured in any organization. (Nelson 2011).

Job performance is a crucial aspect of organizational success, and researchers have extensively studied it over the years. Borman and Motowidlo (1993) identified two essential types of employee behaviour that contribute to organizational effectiveness: task performance and contextual performance. Task performance refers to behaviours directly

involved in producing goods or services, or providing indirect support for the organization's core technical processes. These behaviours are typically rewarded by the organization and are essential for achieving its goals. Task performance is a critical component of job performance, as it directly impacts the organization's ability to deliver its products or services.

The world Health Organization WHO (2006) described performance as one that operates in such ways the one will be responsive, reasonable, competent and proficient to achieve the paramount outcomes whether organizational, educational, security or health and others. This is because poor performance in the educational sector due to abysmal performance in discharging duties of teachers and lecturers or other categories of employees may lead to poor and low outcomes of both products and services (Kruk and Freedom,2008). This is the main reason Noe (2008) state that five approaches could be adopted to measure performance namely attributes, behaviour, comparative, quality and result approach. The comparative approach evaluates performance by comparing individual performance to another person performing a related job through a ranking that involves arrangement from highest to the last person. Ali (2020) opined that improvements of people is key to organizational objectives. Nelson (2011) opines that every organization must have arrangements that outline ways of measuring the performance of organisational tasks. Force distribution can be described as putting employee with other employees in the working group by allocating points to one and ranking them. The paired comparison involves supervisors comparing every employee with other employees in the work group by allocating a point to one using the point to compare to those of pairs performing better.

Armstrong (2009) asserted that the major advantage of the Comparative approach is that an employee's performance needs to separate from others, it is limited in that it does not measure performance against absolute standards. The attributes approach entails Identifying employee attributes needed for organizational success and here employee performance is evaluated according to Identify attributes. The

graphic scale is adopted in where the supervisor rates the employee on particular attributes with a standard scale. Noe et al (2008) asserts that although the approach is reliable and results normally valid across a range, it does bring defensiveness among employees, as performance standards are usually unclear and may be interpreted differently. The behaviour approach which emphasis behaviour needs to be discharged for effectiveness in a given task. The supervision evaluates performance by identifying the level at which employees display the regained behaviour needed for a particular task. The tool used includes critical incidence, behaviourally achieved rating scale, behaviour observation scale and Organizational behaviour modification (Noe et al 2008) the major merit of this approach is that it gives an opportunity for feedback on their performance by employees and managers but its weakness is that it assumes there is one best way to deliver a given job (Not el al 2008).

The correlation between Emotional Intelligence and work performance is probably a multifaceted result of the indirect advantages of social capital and the direct advantages of effectively integrating emotions into decision-making processes. Emotional intelligence should assist workers in developing a strong social network that may provide them with enhanced access to important information and resources that support job performance (Sparrowe et al., 2001). Emotional intelligence (EI) may help people improve job performance by allowing them to manage their emotions to enhance tasks and reduce emotions that hinder them. Someone with great emotional intelligence understands the relationship between emotions and thinking and can adjust their emotions to improve their cognitive abilities. This will assist individuals in making optimal selections and aiding others to do the same, perhaps enhancing their work performance (Côté and Miners, 2006).

Cronyism

Newman, (2021) stated that the unrepentant cronyism of the Old Order concentrated power in the monarch, feudal landlords, privileged merchants, the royal bureaucracy, and the church against the laborers,

peasants, artisans, and discriminated religious groups. In essence, the concept “cronyism” is not a new concept. It has been in existence for a very long time which the failure to eliminate it in the olden days has given it the privilege to find its way in to the present days of human being. In alignment with this Hodgson, (2019) argued that “cronyism has had much greater longevity than markets: it extends back to our simian ancestors. Trade in some form has been in existence for tens of thousands of years, but cronyism goes back millions of years. As a consequence, cronyism and corruption are not recent impositions on a market economy caused by large corporations, democracy, or whatever. They are instead long-standing aspects of the human condition that may be restrained in the modern era only with the rise of modern, relatively autonomous systems of state law”.

Cronyism is defined as favoritism shown by the superior to his or her subordinate based on their relationship, rather than the latter’s capability or qualification, in exchange for the latter’s personal loyalty Khatri and Tsang (2003). The individuals holding power of any societal angle always seek for those who are loyal and submissive to their will and this makes them to consider people of such nature to get access to public or private appointment at the expense of neglecting those who are more qualified and capable to fill the positions. It is clear and understood that the cronies follow their leaders’ order at all-time even if it goes against the wish of the constitutional provisions of the state. Khatri and Tsang (2003) further buttressed his definition with the position that Cronyism is obviously against the principle of fair employee appraisal and is an unethical management practice. Reports of cronyism in the media are usually associated with a certain degree of moral rebuke. Pearce, (2022) in line with the previous assertion, he explained that Cronyism therefore corresponds to expenditure of public resources to pay for (political or other) benefits enjoyed by politicians only, even if it may promote mismanagement and further waste. This will also typically involve discrimination of people more suitable for those jobs. Cronyism certainly encourages biasness which causes social unrest within and among people of the same state. It gives the

opportunity to the clan or tribe in power to subdue others who are also entitled to the benefits. Pearce, (2022) concluded in its study that “cronyism is widespread across the pool of new hires and not specific to a given group of workers, at least as one could define them with the variables available here (schooling, gender, age, experience, job level, and hourly pay). The cronyism is not restricted to a particular state rather it is found in every human society. Their conclusion justifies the positions that there is no just society only that degree of cronyism varies among the states. And this can be seen in Newman, (2021) who posited that when liberty triumphs over power, cronyism is reduced; when the opposite occurs, privileges increase. A well-established constitutional state enjoys maximum freedom from cronyism but an opposite of such state enjoys cronyism at the expense of downgrading and destructing its domain. He further explained that Cronyism is due to the corrupting nature of government power and only by eliminating it can society destroy such favoritism.

Dinara, (2015) claimed through their study “that Nepotism and cronyism damage exactly the kinds of social relationships that make for a humane and tolerable workplace and foster organizational performance. There is absolutely no evidence that nepotism and cronyism facilitate the kinds of personal relationships I-O psychologists would seek, and there is substantial research evidence (as well as the personal conclusions of anyone who has ever seen nepotism and cronyism in operation in an actual organization) that nepotism and cronyism undermine organizations and the people who work in them.” This claim substantiates the fact that cronyism is in the same league with nepotism. And the damage they cause cannot be overlooked because it obstructs effective productivity expected among workers in their place of works which in turn put the society in array.

TUR (2012) takes cronyism to be a “partiality to long-standing friends, especially by appointing them to positions of authority, regardless of their qualifications, or granting privileged access to economic opportunities and/or preferential treatment in dealing with administrative procedures. In the economic sphere, “crony capitalism”

is a term describing an economy in which success in business depends on close relationships between business people and government officials. It may be exhibited by favoritism in the distribution of legal permits, government grants, special tax breaks, or other forms of state interventionism”. This position introduced how cronyism operates in capitalism. It informs that there exists a cordial relationship between the people in position of public authority and businessmen where the latter considers the former in taking public decisions. However, this is advantageous to the government and the businessmen but the masses suffer at such decision because the private investors exploit them and the government neglects as long the private-ownership remains loyal. Klein, Holmes, Foss, Terjesen, and Pepe, (2024) cited Chalmers (2022) who positioned that ‘‘cronyism and capitalism cannot be distinguished conceptually’’. And this is because cronyism exists when ‘‘business success hinges on relationships with government officials who can provide resources, regulatory exemptions, and other benefits that are unavailable to less politically connected individuals and firms’’ (Klein et al., 2022). Cronyism and capitalism favours those that have influence or hand in government neglecting the less privileged ones. It creates classes in the society like capitalism considers haves and have-nots. Cronyism and capitalism are two sides of a coin that cannot be separated.

Standard Operating Procedures

Standardization involves creating solutions for recurring problems across different fields. This process entails developing, establishing, and implementing standards. In the context of quality systems, standards are the ultimate outcome of standardization efforts, typically taking the form of quality documents or related materials (Akyar, 2012). The introduction of standard ideology towards any organization programme or duties make it quality and problem-free because it is designed to meet the objectives of the organization. The definition of this standardization paves way for us to understand what standard operating procedure connotes.

According to Standard Operating Procedures under World Health Organization (2014) A Standard Operating Procedure is a document which describes the regularly recurring operations to ensure that the operations are carried out correctly (quality) and always in the same manner (consistency). The Standard Operating Procedure serves as a manual need to be followed by workers of a specific organization to achieve the goals set and also to quality to the organization. It serves more as a solution to problems that are facing or liable to rise against the organization in future. In furtherance, (Akyar, 2012) also defined SOP as a detailed document outlining the steps an operator should take to perform a specific task. It covers the operation's purpose, required equipment and materials, setup and operation procedures, maintenance and shutdown protocols, safety considerations, troubleshooting, and spare parts information. SOPs are one of several key documents, including process flowcharts and material specifications that help ensure consistent and efficient operation of a process. At this space one understands that SOPs are an important tool for organizations that want to improve efficiency, accuracy, and safety in their operations. By providing a clear and comprehensive guide for operators, SOPs can help to reduce errors and improve quality, while also enhancing safety and compliance. Whether you're looking to improve your organization's performance or simply want to ensure that your processes are running smoothly, SOPs are an essential resource to consider.

Ministry of Health, (2010) In the context of Health Information Systems (HIS), Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) are written guidelines that outline the steps for managing significant activities related to HIS. These SOPs should reflect best practices in information management, be practical, and usable within the HIS subsystem. They cover various aspects of HIS management, including data collection, analysis, storage, processing, and record-keeping, as well as the management of devices and tools used to handle data. Although this definition is specific to the Health angle but it never changes the primary focus of Sops which is efficiency, quality and accuracy in carrying out tasks or duties assigned to workers in their places of work.

In line with this Quality Improvement Secretariat (QIS) (2019) noted that A Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) is a set of step-by-step instructions that helps healthcare providers perform routine operations efficiently and effectively.

The goal of SOPs is to ensure quality, consistency, and accuracy in service delivery, while minimizing errors and miscommunication. By providing clear guidelines, SOPs enable service providers to follow established norms and standards, which benefits both clients and providers. Additionally, SOPs help supervisors evaluate institutional service standards and ensure that they meet expected levels of quality. Standard Operating Procedures for the Health Management Information System Data Management Procedures Manual I (2020) contributed that the Data Management Procedures Manual for Health Information Systems (HIS) outlines the practices and procedures for managing, coordinating, monitoring, and supervising HIS data. It covers issues related to data collection, quality, and accessibility, providing a framework for effective data management.

Methodology

This study employed descriptive research design to answer the objectives of the study. This method allows the researcher to test the study's hypotheses and make generalisation of findings (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). The target population comprised academic and administrative staff members at Benue State University, Makurdi, and University of Ilorin. The total population is 6,717 consisting of Professorial cadres to Graduate Assistant, and Registrar to the ranks of Executive officers in academics and administrative staff respectively and informed members of National Universities Commission, Ministries of Education and Head of Service. The sample size for this study was determined by adopting the statistical method of Taro Yamane as follow:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + e^2(N)}$$

Where, **n**= Sample size; **N**= Population; **e**= Level of significance (0.05)

$$n = \frac{6,717}{1+0.05^2(6,717)} = \frac{6,717}{1+0.0025(6,717)} = \frac{6,717}{1+16.7925}$$

$n = 377.5 = 378$ approximately

This study’s sample size is three hundred and seventy-eight (378) respondents.

This study employed stratified sampling technique. Stratified Sampling divided the target population into strata based on the University, Faculty, and Departments. Participants were randomly selected from each stratum to ensure representation across universities and faculties. The table below shows the stratified processes.

Table 1 *Stratified Sampling*

Selected Institutions	Number of Employees	Stratified Sampling
Benue State University (Academic)	983	$\frac{983}{6,717} \times 378 = 55$
Benue State University (Admin)	1,524	$\frac{1,524}{6,717} \times 378 = 86$
University of Ilorin (Academic)	1,221	$\frac{1,221}{6,717} \times 378 = 69$
University of Ilorin (Admin)	2,489	$\frac{2,489}{6,717} \times 378 = 140$
Tetfund Staff	100	$\frac{100}{6,717} \times 378 = 6$
National University Commission	100	$\frac{100}{6,717} \times 378 = 6$
Federal Ministry of Education	150	$\frac{150}{6,717} \times 378 = 8$
Federal Head of Service	150	$\frac{150}{6,717} \times 378 = 8$
Total	6,717	378

Source: Author’s Calculation (2026)

The study followed ethical guidelines and procedures. The ethical approval was sought from Ethical Committee and it was approved. Aftermath, the researcher sought the gatekeepers’ approval for the research to be conducted in their institution and it was granted. A structured close-ended questionnaire based on relevant literature and

expert opinions were developed. The survey was administered face to face to a sample of academic and administrative staff members at the University of Ilorin and Benue State University. The questionnaire captured demographic information, perceptions of nepotism/favouritism and human capital development practices, and self-reported job performance measures. Also, on the reliability test was performed research instrument used in the study using Cronbach's Alpha. Items were deemed internally consistent with 0.733. All Cronbach's Alpha values for the scales are above the suggested threshold of 0.70 (Saunders et al., 2023). Therefore, there is no uncertainty about the internal consistency of the measurements.

This study employed descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. Descriptive statistics was used to summarise the demographic characteristics and key variables while correlation analysis was utilized to examine the relationships between human capital development factors and employee performance using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) of Version 25.

Findings

This study utilised a face-to-face questionnaire to collect data. The researcher aimed to obtain 378 responses from participants at selected institutions. Over a period of a month, 328 respondents provided complete responses, while 50 responses were not received or discarded based on incomplete filling of responses. The final response rate of 86.77% of 328 respondents indicates a strong dataset, sufficient for drawing valid conclusions in this study.

Table 2: Demographic Information of the Respondents

Demographic Constructs	Count	Percentage
	Gender	
Male	202	61.6
Female	126	38.4
	Qualification	
NCE/OND	5	1.5
BSc./HND	105	32.0
Masters	124	37.8
PhD	85	25.9
Others	9	2.7
	Age	
18-35 years	55	16.8
36-43 years	145	44.2
44-53 years	87	26.5
54-63 years	40	12.2
64 years and above	1	.3
Total	328	100.0

Source: Author’s Survey (2026)

Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Gender distributions revealed that the total number of males was 202 (61.6%) and female counterparts were 126 (38.4%). This implies that the sample is male-dominated, with approximately three out of every five respondents being male. Also, respondents’ educational qualification revealed that those NCE/OND were 5 (1.5%), BSc./HND were 105 (32.0%), Masters were 124 (37.8%), PhD were 85 (25.9%) while those chosen others were 9 (2.7%). From the analysis, the largest proportion of respondents (37.8%) hold a Master's degree. Regarding respondents’ age distribution, it shows that those participants between 18-35 years were 55 (16.8%), 36-43 years were 145 (44.2%), 44-53 years were 87 (26.5%), 54-63 years were 40 (12.2%), 64 years and above were 1 (0.3%). The implication is that the largest proportion of

respondents (44.2%) falls within the 36-43 age bracket, indicating a relatively young and middle-aged workforce.

H01: There is no significant relationship between human capital politics and employee performance in public tertiary institutions in Nigeria

Table 3
Correlations between HCP and Employee Performance

	HCP01	HCP02	HCP03	JP01	JP02	JP03
Pearson Correlation		.393**	.458**	.450**	.409**	.455**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	1	1	.48	.458	.45
Bootstrap	0	-.001	.004	.001	.001	.002
Std. Error	0	.063	.061	.053	.053	.055
Std. Error	0	.063	.051	.063	.053	.055
Pearson Correlation		.393**	1	.427**	.236**	.198**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	1	.297**	.427**	.236**	.198**
Bootstrap	0	-.001	.000	.000	.000	.000
Std. Error	.063	.063	.058	.087	.065	.056
Std. Error	.051	.051	0 0, 0	.064	.056	.053
		.051	.059	.064	.053	.063
Total		6,717			378	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author’s Survey (2026)

Table 3 presents the correlation coefficients between different dimensions of HCP (HCP01, HCP02, HCP03) and Employee Performance (JP01, JP02, JP03). All correlations between HCP and JP variables are positive and statistically significant at the 0.01 level. This suggests that as HCP improves, employee performance tends to increase. However, the strength of relationships varies, with some being moderate to strong (above 0.40) and others weaker (below 0.30).

The table shows strongest correlations: HCP01 & JP01 ($r = 0.480, p < 0.01$). This indicates a moderately strong positive correlation between

HCP01 (likely training, skills, or knowledge acquisition) and JP01 (a specific aspect of employee performance). This implies that employees who receive more training or skill development perform better in their job roles. Similarly, HCP01 & JP03 ($r = 0.458$, $p < 0.01$) suggests that HCP01 is an important predictor of JP03, likely reflecting an aspect of competency or productivity improvement through training. Also, HCP02 & JP01 ($r = 0.427$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a moderate correlation suggests that HCP02 (potentially work experience or career development programs) influences JP01 significantly.

The table also shows moderate correlations: HCP01 & JP02 ($r = 0.402$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates a moderate but significant link between HCP01 and JP02, meaning that human capital investment moderately enhances another dimension of job performance. Moreover, HCP03 & JP01 ($r = 0.335$, $p < 0.01$): a moderate relationship suggests that HCP03 (possibly innovation, creativity, or leadership development) plays a role in job performance, but is not as strong as other HCP variables. Similarly, HCP02 & JP02 ($r = 0.326$, $p < 0.01$) indicate a moderate correlation and suggest that HCP02 also contributes to another aspect of job performance, albeit to a lesser degree than HCP01.

The table also have weakest correlations: HCP03 & JP02 ($r = 0.235$, $p < 0.01$); HCP03 & JP03 ($r = 0.287$, $p < 0.01$); and HCP02 & JP03 ($r = 0.198$, $p < 0.01$). These weak but significant correlations indicate that HCP03 and HCP02 may still influence job performance, but their impact is less than that of HCP01. The bootstrap method (1,000 samples) confirms the stability of the correlation estimates. The 95% confidence intervals do not include zero, reinforcing that these relationships are statistically significant and reliable.

The Pearson correlation analysis confirms a significant relationship between HCP and employee performance. This study reveals a significant relationship between HCP and employee performance. The HCP01 (training and skill development) has the strongest relationship, while HCP02 and HCP03 (educational qualifications and background, and innovation or leadership development) have weaker relationships. The significance value (Sig.) helps determine if the correlation is

statistically significant. A p-value (Sig.) of less than 0.05 indicates significance at the 5% level, while less than 0.01 means significance at the 1% level. Hence, there is a significant relationship between HCP and job performance in the selected universities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings in Table 3 demonstrate that Human Capital Politics (HCP) is significantly associated with employee job performance, yet a critical synthesis reveals that this relationship is deeply conditioned by the political allocation of developmental resources rather than by human capital inputs alone. While the positive and statistically significant correlations confirm that improvements in HCP correspond with enhanced performance outcomes, the uneven strength of these relationships suggests that human capital is filtered through political structures that determine who accesses opportunities, how competencies are deployed, and which forms of performance are rewarded. The strongest correlations, particularly between HCP01 and JP01 and JP03, indicate that politically mediated access to training, skills acquisition, and knowledge development exerts the most immediate influence on performance. This finding aligns with Eseyin's (2014) and Ireland and Hitt's (2013) conception of human capital as a utilitarian stock of skills and knowledge mobilized to achieve organizational goals. However, viewed through a political lens, these results suggest that training functions not merely as a developmental tool but as a politically distributed resource, echoing Easton's characterization of politics as the authoritative allocation of values. Employees who are politically positioned to receive training are consequently better equipped to meet task performance expectations, as conceptualized by Borman and Motowidlo (1993). However, the correlations remain moderate rather than strong, indicating that even politically favoured access to training does not automatically translate into optimal performance, particularly where institutional processes, performance appraisal systems, and organizational cultures fail to fully support skill utilization.

Moreover, the weaker correlations associated with HCP02 and HCP03 illuminate the structural contradictions inherent in Human Capital

Politics. Although educational qualifications, experience, innovation, and leadership capacity are theoretically central to human capital development (Morrill, 2010; Sharma, 2012), their limited relationship with job performance suggests that political interference undermines their productive potential. In politicized organizational environments, credentials and experience may lose their signalling value if advancement and recognition are driven by loyalty rather than competence. This interpretation is consistent with Khatri and Tsang's (2003) and Dinara's (2015) arguments that cronyism corrodes meritocratic systems and weakens the motivational foundations of performance. When innovation and leadership (HCP03) are embedded within political patronage networks, they may be perceived as threats to established power structures rather than assets to be leveraged, thereby constraining their impact on performance outcomes. Furthermore, the weak correlations may reflect the absence or poor enforcement of Standard Operating Procedures, which are designed to depoliticize organizational processes by standardizing expectations, roles, and performance criteria (WHO, 2014; Akyar, 2012). Without such procedural safeguards, Human Capital Politics amplifies discretion, bias, and inconsistency, limiting the extent to which advanced human capital attributes translate into measurable job performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study, based on a comparative analysis, has found that staff performance is significantly improved by investing in human capital through training, learning, skill development, academic growth, well-organized career paths, access to professional development, perceived organizational support, a decent work environment, and welfare incentives. It was evident that frequent participation in professional development programmes among faculty and administrative members will lead to greater efficiency and commitment to their professions, thereby improving institutional production. This was shown in qualitative analysis, where resentful staff members, institutional loyalty is weakened, and the effectiveness of the academic system suffers when

they believe that career development is determined more by personal connections than by ability. This kind of prejudice will limit academic quality, information transfer, and innovation by undermining the institutions' capacity to maximize the whole potential of their employees.

The study further validated that job performance and HCP are much influenced by the degree of nepotism or at best favouritism in staff selection. Indeed, there were strong concerns about favouritism and nepotism in staff hiring, selection and promotion policies impairing meritocracy, which sometimes resulted in the employment of less competent workers trying to fulfil performance standards. Meanwhile, suppose this approach continues in Nigerian universities. In that case, it will stifle staff creativity, lower employee motivation among those who believe the system is unjust, and diminish the institutions' effectiveness in achieving academic excellence.

It was also uncovered that job performance is strongly influenced by the politics surrounding the use of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) in personnel selection for HCP, as evidenced by the mind-up output. This implies that SOPs exist, but their application has not been fully consistent or well communicated, indicating how bureaucratic inefficiencies and nepotism may compromise merit-based selection procedures, thereby excluding qualified people and including less qualified applicants in capacity-building programs. Subsequently, suboptimal staff performance will result, stemming from underqualified or poorly trained staff failing to meet institutional standards. Moreover, the unequal implementation of SOPs was also noted, which may create some uncertainty and demotivation among staff members, thereby lowering overall production and creativity in academic institutions.

From the analysis, it can be established that in Nigerian universities, the relationships between politics, HCP, and job performance are closely entwined with governance structures, institutional policies, influence of personal relationships, political interference, corruption, lack of accountability, and cultural and ethnic biases. For example, political factors were found to affect the distribution of resources, the selection

of top university officials, and the establishment of instructional programs, thereby influencing the quality of HCP within the academic system.

Finally, sound arguments, based on a critical analysis, have been brought to the fore, illustrating the interaction between politics and human capital development (HCD) and job performance in Nigerian universities. It points out that investments in training and promotion, as well as research support, are expected to be the key factors driving an institution's productivity, but political interference and ineffective governance policies are severely weakening the effectiveness of these interventions. Human resource recruitment, promotion, and budgetary allocations have been politicized, and as a result, this has embedded a culture of patronage rather than professionalism, which is supposed to strengthen the motivational and performance-enhancing effects of HCP initiatives. This set of findings can be attributed to the broader corruption in the Nigerian public sector, as merit is often compromised in favour of politically loyal individuals. Nevertheless, pockets of best practice are also detected in the research at the University of Ilorin, a federal university, as opposed to what is observed at Benue State University, a state-owned university.

Recommendations

Following the constructive and critical study's findings and conclusions drawn from them, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. National University Commission should be empowered through executive order to make Universities management comply with the constant provision of staff training, learning, and development programs, and capacity-building seminars in order to enhance their HCP and job performance. The programme's accreditation should be tied to evidence of attendance. This will enhance staff development by ensuring the requisite knowledge, skills, abilities, and competencies.
2. University Standard Merit-Based bill should be enacted to serve as a guide for university management to maintain standard policies that prioritise merit-based recruitment and selection for

staff development to reduce the danger of nepotism/favouritism on HCP, which affects job performance. This implies that if there are strict recruiting policies involving independent selection panels and external monitoring, such as by a civil society group, it will help reduce favouritism and ensure appropriate selections based on competency and credentials.

3. An executive bill needs to be enacted to have an agency call the University Training fund to provide adequate funds through the federation account, and the agency will also serve as a monitor for how selections are being made by the management of various universities. Thus, this will empower University management to put systems in place to measure and evaluate how human capital expenditures affect employment success, thereby ensuring that training initiatives complement national and institutional development agendas.

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